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From Statistic to stories

How Dutch news outlets
present CBS labor market
statistics

Research report

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Abstract

Governmental statistics, such as those produced by the Dutch *Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek* (CBS), play a crucial role in informing public debate and policy decisions. However, the public typically encounters these statistics through media reporting, making their interpretation dependent on journalistic mediation. To examine how such information is conveyed, this study investigates which types of information are most frequently omitted, preserved and added when journalists report on CBS labor market statistics.

We conducted a quantitative content analysis to compare news articles ($n = 149$) with the corresponding CBS press releases ($n = 93$), focusing on their depiction of contextual information, uncertainty and personalized sourcing. This comparison demonstrates that journalists selectively add and omit different types of information. Indicators of uncertainty and technical contextual details, such as dataset references and calculation adjustments, are often omitted, whereas information from external sources, expert quotes and personalization are frequently added.

Additionally, we show that news articles based on embargoed press releases more frequently include external sources, calculation adjustments and personalization. Altogether, these findings suggest that the addition and omission in news articles results from an interplay between time constraints and news value, thereby providing a basis for future efforts to improve the public communication of official statistics.

Keywords: content analysis, labor market statistics, journalistic mediation, news reporting, press release, uncertainty communication, contextual information, personalized sourcing, embargo.

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1. Introduction

The economic and social state of a country is often summarized and communicated in statistical data (Holt, 2008). Consequently, statistics play a central role in society, influencing both public debate and policy decisions (Giovannini, 2008). Official statistical data are produced in national statistical offices, such as the *Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek* (CBS) in the Netherlands. CBS has the lawful task to collect, process and publish reliable statistics about the Dutch society and economy.

Among various economic indicators, CBS has a responsibility to publish official labor market statistics. These statistics generally describe labor demand (e.g. jobs, vacancies, enterprises), labor supply (e.g. (un)employment, participation), workforce characteristics (e.g. composition, demographics) and macroeconomic indicators (e.g. GDP, productivity) (ILO, 2017). Labor market statistics provide important insights into the economic performance and overall wellbeing of a country (Gomes, 2015). As a result, these statistics play a crucial role for policymakers in guiding economic planning and social policy (Blanchard and Katz, 1999).

Given their societal relevance, CBS statistics often inform reporting by news media. Notably, national statistic offices are among the most frequently cited data sources for journalists (Cushion, Lewis and Callaghan, 2017). To facilitate news reporting, CBS typically provides press releases to major news outlets. Consequently, the general public often encounters statistical information indirectly through media coverage rather than direct access to the official source (Spiegelhalter, 2017). In this way, journalists play a critical role in mediating the communication and public understanding of official statistics.

In news reporting, journalists do not merely depict data, but also actively construct context (Capurro *et al.*, 2021). To engage readers and make complex data more accessible, journalists often employ techniques such as framing, stylistic devices and dramatization (Capurro *et al.*, 2021; Vonk, Bos and van Sebille, 2025). As a result, newspaper articles do not simply reproduce statistical information from press releases, but reshape its presentation and emphasis, potentially altering how the original data are interpreted (Vonc, Bos and van Sebille, 2025). To better understand the translation of CBS press releases into news articles, this study compares both sources on the topic of labor market statistics.

1.1. Challenges in reporting statistical data

Recent reports have raised concerns about the ability of journalists to correctly reproduce statistical data. Specifically, some studies have established that news reports involving statistic information appear to follow a trend of minimal disclosure, rarely mentioning all relevant information (Cushion, Lewis and Callaghan, 2017;

Bethäuser, Menold and Winker, 2025). For instance, a large-scale analysis of BBC news found that statistical information was vague or lacked sufficient contextual explanation in a majority of cases (64.8%) (Cushion, Lewis and Callaghan, 2017). Such omissions by journalists can lead to incomplete and potentially misleading representations of the underlying data (Heston, 2024).

Several explanations have been suggested for these recurring issues with reports of statistical information. First, analyzing and reporting complete datasets requires a considerable investment of time, which is discouraged by the current speed of news generation and economic considerations (Dempster, Sutherland and Keogh, 2022; Bethäuser, Menold and Winker, 2025). Furthermore, many journalists possess insufficient scientific literacy to correctly interpret statistical information (Bethäuser, Menold and Winker, 2025). Similarly, it has been suggested that mathematics in general has a bad reputation for being complicated among both journalists and newspaper audiences, which leads to the structural omission of math-related and statistical information (Nguyen and Lugo-Ocando, 2016; Bethäuser, Menold and Winker, 2025).

Altogether, these issues can affect the comprehensiveness of journalists' accounts of statistical data. This tendency has been well documented in reporting about science, which also relies heavily on statistical data (Bles *et al.*, 2019). In such contexts, journalists were reported to particularly omit contextual information (Guenther *et al.*, 2019) and indicators of uncertainty (Gal and Geiger, 2022).

1.2. Contextual information in news reporting

Historically, statistics have been described as essentially “numbers in context” (Gal, 2019). Therefore, context remains a crucial factor to correctly interpret the data (Frischemeier and Schnell, 2023). For instance, statistical information loses meaning without information about base rates, time periods and reference classes (Gigerenzer *et al.*, 2008). Macro-economic variables, including labor market statistics from CBS, are often prone to revisions and corrections (Aruoba and Boragan Aruoba, 2008; Fixler, Franciso and Kanal, 2021), thus particularly requiring contextual qualifiers.

Research in science communication shows that contextual information from science articles is often lost in media coverage. Best (2001) described that numbers and statistics are continuously repeated and extracted between different media outlets, and thereby often gradually lose their original context. Empirical studies have also corroborated the structural omission by news reports of contextual factors, such as research conditions, methodology and source information (Seale, 2010; Cushion, Lewis and Callaghan, 2017; Dempster, Sutherland and Keogh, 2022). Although these findings focus on science reporting, they raise concerns that similar issues may occur in news coverage of labor market statistics.

Given that time constraints pose a threat to the comprehensiveness of news reports (Bethäuser, Menold and Winker, 2025), the exclusion of contextual information may also depend on whether a press release is published under embargo. Embargoed press releases are intended to give journalists additional preparation time (Kiernan, 1997), which may facilitate more complete inclusion of contextual details.

1.3. Uncertainty in news reporting

Contextual descriptions can also be used to convey uncertainty, which is inherently part of science, facts and statistics (Dumas-Mallet et al., 2018; Bles et al., 2019; Fiscutean and Rosu, 2025). In the context of official economic statistics, Manski (2015) describes the distinction between transitory and permanent uncertainty. Transitory uncertainty is the result of a time-dependent limitation to the amount of available data. This uncertainty diminishes through later revisions, and is thus often represented in provisional figures. For example, CBS publishes successive provisional estimates of the Gross Domestic Product at fixed time intervals, which are later revised as more complete information becomes available. In contrast, permanent uncertainty is not time-dependent and is often associated with other limitations to the data availability and/or quality. For instance, national statistical offices rely on finite sample sizes and data sources that may contain measurement errors, which cannot be eliminated through subsequent revisions (Manski, 2015).

Evidence from science communication research indicates that uncertainty is not consistently conveyed in news articles about science. Previous content analyses across several scientific domains demonstrated that approximately 36-40% of news articles omit key statements about study limitations, thus giving the impression of enhanced certainty (Pellechia, 1997; Jensen, 2008). Additionally, news reports often leave out relevant mentions of scientific uncertainty, such as denoting preliminary data, knowledge gaps, measurement deficiencies or the requirement for replication (Dumas-Mallet et al., 2018; Guenther et al., 2019; Heidmann & Milde, 2013). Such patterns of omissions may hypothetically also apply to reporting on CBS labor market statistics.

1.4. Personalized sourcing in news reporting

Journalists also often supplement news stories with personalized sourcing, which includes both personalization and expert citations. Personalization is a narrative strategy of presenting facts together with personal stories of individual people (Vonk, Bos and van Sebille, 2025). These personal aspects are believed to result in enhanced audience engagement, through fostering deeper emotional connection. As a result, personalization is widely used in news reporting and represents a common journalistic technique (Krämer and Peter, 2020).

Personalization is mostly relevant for issues that heavily affect the daily lives of people, such as burn-outs, public health and elections (Krämer and Peter, 2020). Since labor market developments and unemployment also directly impact people's economic security and overall wellbeing, we hypothesize that personalization plays an influential role in reporting on these topics.

Besides personalization, news articles also often contain citations from expert sources (Boyce, 2006). These expert citations differ from personalization because they represent authority rather than individual experience (Boyce, 2006). The citations are used to explain, contextualize or expand upon complex information. At the same time, consulting experts is often considered a means of enhancing the credibility of an article, making it a common journalistic strategy (Bossema *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, In the context of labor market reporting, expert sourcing may be particularly influential, as labor market statistics are multidimensional and often require interpretation regarding their causes, implications and policy relevance (ILO, 2017).

1.5. News reports on CBS statistics

Overall, prior research has established that journalistic reporting is often associated with the addition of personalized sourcing and the omission of contextual information or uncertainty indicators, particularly when covering statistical data. Yet, it remains largely unclear whether these alterations to the supporting information affect the news representation of official statistics, such as CBS labor market data. Moreover, journalistic reporting operates under the constraint of time pressure, and the use of embargoed press releases may further influence how information is included and adapted in news articles.

Simultaneously, addressing this research gap is crucial because the public primarily encounters such statistics through mediated news reports, and editorial choices may therefore affect interpretation. This issue is further underscored by evidence that contemporary news reporting increasingly relies on statistical data (Nguyen and Lugo-Ocando, 2016; Cushion, Lewis and Callaghan, 2017). Moreover, this reliance is expected to grow further in the future, should the role of big data in society continue to expand (Nguyen and Lugo-Ocando, 2016).

1.6. Research questions

To conclude, labor market statistics are increasingly relevant in society and policy development. Yet, it remains largely unclear to what extent their representation involves the addition and omission of supporting information, and how these patterns are influenced by time constraints. To address this issue, the proposed study aims to investigate the following research question:

What types of information are omitted, preserved or added when Dutch news outlets cover CBS labor market statistics, relative to the original press release?

To address this research question, several subquestions are proposed:

- To what extent is contextual information from CBS press releases omitted, preserved or added in news articles?
- To what extent are uncertainty indicators from CBS press releases omitted, preserved or added in news articles?
- To what extent is personalized sourcing from CBS press releases omitted, preserved or added in news articles?

To answer the proposed research questions, we employed a quantitative content analysis, based on its established use in similar media portrayal studies (Sumner *et al.*, 2014; Bethäuser, Menold and Winker, 2025; Vonk, Bos and van Sebille, 2025). The analysis focused on manifest content to systematically compare news articles on labor market statistics with the corresponding CBS press releases. Through this comparison, we aimed to identify similarities and differences in the representation of contextual information, uncertainty and personalized sourcing. The prevalence of these different types of information was then used to identify structural omissions and/or additions between the CBS press releases and news articles. In addition, we compared articles resulting from press releases distributed under embargo with those released simultaneously with public publication. This comparison enabled us to examine how potential time constraints might influence the likelihood of omissions or additions in news reporting.

2.1. Data collection

The quantitative content analysis jointly evaluated CBS press releases about the labor market alongside subsequent news articles. The selection of news articles was intended to capture the breadth of the Dutch media landscape, and thus included the five largest Dutch newspapers in combination with the five largest news websites: *Algemeen Dagblad*, *De Telegraaf*, *De Volkskrant*, *NRC*, *Trouw*, *NU.nl*, *AD.nl*, *NOS.nl*, *Telegraaf.nl* and *RTL.nl* (Beens, 2023; Nationaal Media onderzoek, 2025). However, due to the absence of relevant coverage of CBS labor market statistics in some outlets, the final dataset comprised articles from *Algemeen Dagblad*, *De Telegraaf*, *De Volkskrant*, *NRC*, *Trouw*, and *NU.nl* (Figure 1). We included articles published between 1 January 2023 and 31 December 2025 to capture the most recent trends in the reporting of labor market statistics.

We first collected news articles from the selected sources through LexisUni (LexisNexis, 2026), using the query indicated below. The search combines mentions of CBS with at least one Dutch keyword that indicates a key labor market statistic. These keywords were compiled in consultation with CBS. Additionally, the query restricts the keywords to a maximum distance of 20 words, which was determined empirically to minimize irrelevant results (Appendix 1).

(Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek) AND (arbeidsmarkt OR beroepsbevolking OR arbeids OR werkloos* OR werkloz* OR werknemer OR werkgelegenheid OR "bijstandsuitkering*" OR baan* OR vacature* OR WW* OR deeltijd* OR ZZP OR flex*) W/20 CBS*

Articles were first manually screened and only included if they explicitly reference a labor market statistic, categorized by labor demand, labor supply, workforce characteristics and macroeconomic indicators (see section *Introduction*). Articles that did not contain a numerical value or that referred to statistics outside of the labor market domain were excluded (Figure 1).

For each included article, we identified the first reported labor market statistic, as the central focus of news articles is typically presented at the beginning (Norambuena, Horning and Mitra, 2020). This statistic was then used to retrieve the original press release by searching the CBS online archive for a corresponding statistic within one year of the article's publication date. The one-year window was selected to minimize the possibility of missing a connection between articles and press releases. If no corresponding statistic was identified in a press release, the news article was excluded from analysis (Figure 1) as this would prevent the intended comparison. Altogether, the data collection resulted in a dataset of 149 news articles (Figure 1), corresponding to 94 distinct press releases.

Figure 1. Data collection method.

To account for multiple news articles originating from a single press release, we grouped news articles by their CBS source prior to data analysis. This strategy ensures that each press release is coded once.

Additionally, the embargo status of each press release was established based on article type. According to CBS, unembargoed articles only include the monthly and quarterly releases, which report unemployment levels and broad labor market indicators. All other articles, generally focused on thematic studies or a specific labor market statistic, are typically embargoed. In the dataset, this distinction corresponded to 34 news articles derived from 19 non-embargoed press releases and 115 articles associated with 74 embargoed press releases.

2.2. Coding process

To analyze these articles, we developed a codebook (Table 1 & Appendix 2). The codebook enabled a systematic assessment of the presence or absence of the content categories contextual information, uncertainty and personalized sourcing. First, uncertainty was coded using the framework developed by Manski (2015), distinguishing between transitory and permanent uncertainty (Table 1). Additionally, we distinguished between explicit and contextual indicators, to capture variations in the salience of uncertainty. Second, the prevalence of different types of contextual information was evaluated by noting their presence or absence (Table 1), similar to the approaches of Bethäuser, Menold and Winker (2025) and Guenther et al. (2019). Third, the presence of personalized sourcing, either personalization or expert citations, was recorded together with the source affiliation (Table 1), following the approaches developed by Vonk, Bos and van Sebille (2025) and Bossema et al. (2019).

Table 1. Codebook outline. Representation of the coding variables and their possible coding values across the different content categories. Coding variables include indicators of uncertainty (Uncertainty), mentions of CBS as the source (Source), references to the original dataset (Dataset), calculation adjustments applied to the statistic (Adjustments), supplementary information from external sources (Information), temporal comparisons of the statistic (Period), quotes highlighting a personal action or experience (Personalization), type of personal actor (Personalization affiliation), quotes from authoritative figures (Experts) and type of authoritative figure (Expert affiliation). Coding variables are measured using either binary or nominal scales, with the corresponding categories indicated for each variable.

Content category	Coding variable	Coding values
Uncertainty	Uncertainty	Nominal (absence, contextual transitory, explicit transitory, contextual permanent, explicit permanent)
Contextual information	Source	Binary (presence, absence)
	Dataset	Binary (presence, absence)
	Adjustments	Binary (presence, absence)
	Information	Binary (presence, absence)
	Period	Binary (presence, absence)
Personalized sourcing	Personalization	Binary (presence, absence)
	Personalization affiliation	Nominal (Employee, employer, unemployed, government)
	Expert	Binary (presence, absence)
	Expert affiliation	Nominal (CBS, university, financial institution, Union, UWV, employer, government)

For both news articles and press releases, the unit of analysis was the entire article to account for the representation of information in different sections. However, certain coding categories in the preliminary codebook (Appendix 2) focus specifically on the “highlighted figure”, which is defined as the first CBS statistic referenced in the news article. This concept was introduced to manage the complexity of CBS press releases, which often detail many distinct statistics with varying context and uncertainty. Therefore, to code these variables accurately, we focus on the statistic most relevant to the news article rather than the entire text.

2.3. Intercoder reliability

To ensure the reproducibility of the results, intercoder reliability was first established. A random 10% subsample of articles ($n = 15$) was independently coded by a second coder using the proposed codebook (Appendix 2). Prior to formal coding, the coders discussed the codebook and jointly coded a pilot set of two articles to familiarize themselves with the process. The agreement between coders was evaluated using Cohen's kappa (Cohen, 1960). The average score was 0.95, and all individual codes exceeded the threshold of 0.81 (Appendix 4) for almost perfect agreement (Landis and Koch, 1977).

2.4. Data analysis

The goal of the data analysis was to summarize how Dutch news outlets report CBS labor market statistics, focusing on the presence of uncertainty, personalized sourcing and contextual information. To this end, the coded data were analyzed at the level of article–press release pairs by comparing the presence of each variable between the two sources. This comparison allowed for the identification of correspondence, additions (variables present in the news article but not in the press release) and omissions (variables present in the press release but not in the news article).

To determine the association between the embargo status and article content, we employed a chi-square test (McHugh, 2013). For both additions and omissions, frequency distributions were calculated for both articles based on embargoed and non-embargoed press releases. The subsequent calculation of the chi-square statistic was done in R (R Core Team, 2026). Multiple testing corrections were performed using the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995).

Analysis of the 149 news articles reveals a strongly skewed distribution in media coverage across the set of 93 CBS press releases (Figure 2). Most press releases generate only one associated article ($n = 59$), with progressively fewer producing several articles. Coverage beyond three articles per press release is relatively uncommon ($n = 4$).

Figure 2. News coverage of press releases. Distribution of the number of news articles covering each CBS labor market press releases ($n = 93$).

3.1. Translation of contextual information

The inclusion of contextual information in both press releases and news articles varies substantially across categories (Table 2). Source information is consistently included in all press releases (100%) and nearly all news articles (98%). In contrast, references to the underlying dataset appear in only a minority of press releases (26.6%) and news articles (8.1%). Similarly, calculation adjustments are infrequently reported in press releases (31.9%) and are almost entirely absent in news articles (2.0%). Information from external sources is relatively uncommon in press releases (17.0%) but frequently included in news articles (75.8%). Finally, periodic comparisons are reported in the majority of both press releases (85.1%) and news articles (77.2%).

Table 2. Representation of contextual information. Percentage occurrence of different forms of contextual information in press releases (n = 93) and news articles (n = 149). Contextual information includes the categories: mentions of CBS as the source (Source), references to the original dataset (Dataset), calculation adjustments for the statistic (Adjustments), supplementary information from external sources (Information) and periodic comparisons of the statistic over time (Period).

Context category	Press release occurrence (%)	News article occurrence (%)
Source	100.0	98.0
Dataset	26.6	8.1
Adjustments	31.9	2.0
Information	17.0	75.8
Period	85.1	77.2

Building on the aggregate patterns observed in Table 2, we conducted a direct comparison between each news article and the associated press release to identify omissions and additions. In the majority of cases where dataset information was missing from the press release, it is never added in the news articles (Figure 3). Alternatively, when such information was provided in the press release, it is still omitted by most news articles. Similarly, calculation adjustments were also absent from the vast majority of news articles, regardless of their representation in the original press releases.

In contrast, while supplementary information from external sources was rarely included in press releases, the majority of news articles add such data (Figure 3). Finally, periodic comparisons show high correspondence with the press release, since inclusion or exclusion is generally mirrored in the news articles.

Figure 3. Comparison of contextual information in news articles and associated press releases. Percentage occurrence of the omission and addition of different types of contextual information in news articles ($n = 149$) relative to the original press releases ($n = 93$). Omissions reflect information present in the press release but not carried over in the subsequent news article, while Additions reflect information not present in the press release but introduced in the news article. Correspondence between news article and press release is shown as Preservation (included in both) and Absence (excluded in both). Contextual information includes the categories: mentions of CBS as the source (Source), references to the original dataset (Dataset), calculation adjustments for the statistic (Adjustments), supplementary information from external sources (Information) and periodic comparisons of the statistic over time (Period).

3.2. Translation of uncertainty

Uncertainty is largely absent from both CBS press releases (67.0%) and, to a greater extent, from news articles (90.6%) (Table 3). When uncertainty is present, it exclusively concerns transitory uncertainty; no instances of permanent uncertainty are observed in any of the press releases or news articles. In press releases, such transitory uncertainty appears in both contextual (19.2%) and explicit mentions (13.8%). In contrast, news articles contain only explicit mentions, present in a minority of instances (9.4%).

Table 3. Representation of uncertainty. Percentage occurrence of different forms of uncertainty in press releases (n= 93) and news articles (n = 149). Uncertainty was coded as either absent (No uncertainty) or present, and further categorized into contextual or explicit, as well as transitory or permanent. Explicit uncertainty refers to a direct reference to uncertainty in the main text of the article, whereas contextual uncertainty is only implied through surrounding information. Transitory and permanent uncertainty are distinguished on whether the uncertainty is indicated to diminish over time.

Type of uncertainty	Press release occurrence (%)	News article occurrence (%)
No uncertainty	67.0	90.6
Contextual transitory	19.2	0.0
Explicit transitory	13.8	9.4
Contextual permanent	0.0	0.0
Explicit permanent	0.0	0.0

When the press release does not include uncertainty, none of the subsequent news articles refer to it (Figure 4). Similarly, only a small minority of the news articles mention uncertainty if the press release contains a contextual reference. The occurrence of uncertainty in news articles increases when the press release includes an explicit reference. Overall, disclosures of uncertainty are never added in news articles and most often omitted, even when explicitly stated in the press release.

Figure 4. Comparison of uncertainty in news articles and associated press releases. Percentage occurrence of uncertainty in news articles (n = 149) as a function of the type of uncertainty in the original press release (n = 93). The y-axis represents the frequency of the exclusion (blue) and inclusion (green) of explicit mentions of uncertainty in news articles. The x-axis shows the observed categories of uncertainty in press releases along with their frequencies, corresponding to Table 3.

3.3. Translation of personalized sourcing

Personalized sourcing is entirely absent in CBS press releases (0%) (Table 4). In contrast, the majority of news articles cite at least one expert (57.7%), while personalization also appears in a smaller proportion (12.8%).

Table 4. Representation of contextual information in press releases. Percentage occurrence of different forms of personalized sourcing in press releases (n = 93) and news articles (n = 149). Personalized sourcing was coded as quotes highlighting a personal action or experience (Personalization) and quotes from authoritative figures explaining a development (Experts)

Personalized sourcing category	Press release occurrence (%)	News article occurrence (%)
Personalization	0.0	12.8
Experts	0.0	57.7

The individuals cited under personalization spanned multiple labor market groups, most prominently employees (36.4%) and employers (31.8%) (Figure 5A). Less frequently cited sources were unemployed individuals (13.6%) and representatives from the government (9.1%). Among expert sources, representatives from CBS accounted for the largest portion of citations (36.1%), followed by experts from universities (19.7%) and financial institutions (17.2%) (Figure 5B). Other sources were cited less frequently and included unions (7.4%), industry organizations (7.4%) and government representatives (6.6%).

Figure 5. Types of individuals cited in news articles. Distribution of types and affiliation of the cited sources of both personalization (A) and experts (B) in news articles (n = 149). The x-axis shows the various coded types of individuals, together with their categorization, while the y-axis shows the associated frequency (%).

3.4. Influence of the embargo status

A chi-square test was conducted to examine differences in article content based on embargo status, revealing four significant deviations (Table 5). First, supplementary information from external sources was added significantly more often in news articles when the press release was published under embargo (71.3%) compared with non-embargoed press releases (38.2%). Omissions of such supplementary information were also lower in embargoed cases (0%) compared with non-embargoed articles (17.4%).

In addition, calculation adjustments were omitted significantly less frequently from embargoed press releases (23.5%) than in non-embargoed articles (73.5%) (Table 5). Finally, personalized references were added more often under embargo (16.5%), whereas no such additions were observed in articles based on non-embargoed press releases.

Table 5. Effect of embargo on news article content. Percentage occurrence of omissions and additions for all articles (Average, n = 149), for the subset of articles published under embargo (Embargo, n = 115), and for the subset not under embargo (No embargo, n = 34). The p-value indicates the difference between embargoed and non-embargoed articles, based on a chi-square test, and was adjusted using the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure. If a subset of articles does not allow for additions or omissions due to complete presence or absence of the information in the press releases, the value is denoted as Not Applicable (N.A.). Values in bold represent significant deviations, based on an adjusted p-value < 0.05.

Variable	Category	Average (%)	Embargo (%)	No Embargo (%)	p-value
Uncertainty	Added	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
	Omitted	25.3	32.2	17.6	0.154
Source	Added	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	-
	Omitted	2.0	2.6	0.0	0.798
Dataset	Added	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
	Omitted	17.5	20.0	N.A.	-
Information	Added	62.6	71.3	38.2	8.97e-4
	Omitted	2.24	0.0	17.4	2.71e-4
Period	Added	3.0	3.5	N.A.	-
	Omitted	11.9	14.8	2.9	0.118
Adjustments	Added	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
	Omitted	29.3	23.5	73.5	2.28e-7
Personalization	Added	12.8	16.5	0.0	0.0248
	Omitted	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	-
Expert	Added	57.1	58.3	55.9	0.961
	Omitted	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	-

The aim of this research was to elucidate the difference between news articles and CBS press releases on labor market statistics. Specifically, we analyzed and compared both sources on their representation of uncertainty, contextual information and personalized sourcing. By directly comparing news articles with their original press release, a key strength of the study lies in the ability to identify direct dissimilarities that occur within the news translation process.

4.1. Representation of contextual information

Regarding contextual information, we showed that different types are selectively omitted, added or preserved in the transformation of press releases to news articles. This finding is consistent with previous research showing that journalists do not mechanically transfer all press release information but instead reframe and selectively rework content (Maat and De Jong, 2013; Vonk, Bos and van Sebille, 2025). In our analysis, additions most frequently take the form of information from external sources, whereas dataset specifications and calculation adjustments are commonly omitted. Additionally, we show that source references and periodic comparisons are often preserved.

These observed patterns align with the theory of news factors, which posits that journalists select and frame information based on factors such as prominence, dynamics, conflict, proximity and scope (Schafraad and Van Zoonen, 2019; Boukes, Jones and Vliegthart, 2022). For example, the factor prominence can be attributed to references to elite societal institutions (Schafraad and Van Zoonen, 2019), which may explain the frequent preservation of CBS mentions in news articles. Similarly, dynamics can be reflected in descriptions of temporal context, accounting for the news value of periodic comparisons. In contrast, technical details such as dataset specifications or calculation adjustments hypothetically carry little inherent news value, which could help explain their frequent omission. Thus, the theory of news factors provides a plausible framework for understanding the selective preservation and omission of contextual information.

Furthermore, we found that some of the observed additions and omissions of contextual information depend on the embargo status of the original press release. Notably, when press releases were provided under embargo, omissions of both calculation adjustments and supplementary information occurred less frequently. Although limited research has directly examined the effects of embargoed press releases, one possible explanation is that embargoes are intended to reduce time pressure for journalists, thereby allowing for a more careful and comprehensive representation of the press release (Kiernan, 1997). Reduced time constraints may also

provide journalists with the opportunity to perform additional research, which could explain the observation that information from external sources was more frequently added in embargoed cases. Under this hypothesis, this research suggests that the use of embargoes may facilitate more comprehensive news reporting, providing a potential practical strategy for statistical agencies such as CBS to enhance the uptake of information.

However, a key caveat to these conclusions is that the observed differences between embargoed and non-embargoed articles may partly reflect variations in article type rather than embargo status alone. CBS provides distinct types of articles under embargo (see section *Methods*), which can differ in the content and focus of information they present. These differences may hypothetically have contributed to the deviations observed in the chi-square analysis. While this represents a methodological limitation that calls for caution in interpreting the results, its overall impact is likely limited. Although article types may vary in focus or the specific statistics they report, they all cover general labor market descriptors, so these variations are not expected to substantially affect the overall handling of information.

More broadly, this study is subject to several other limitations. First, the assumed link between individual press releases and corresponding news articles cannot be definitively established. Nonetheless, the assumption that news articles are most often directly based on press releases is supported both through communication with CBS and prior research in science communication (Schwartz *et al.*, 2012; Sumner *et al.*, 2014). Second, the analysis relies predominantly on binary coding, which may fail to capture more nuanced differences in how information is presented. As a result, instances where press releases and news articles receive the same coding classification may still differ in terms of phrasing, emphasis or sourcing. However, because the study focuses on the presence or absence of key information rather than its precise formulation, this limitation is unlikely to substantially affect the overall conclusions.

To gain further insight into the reasons behind selective omissions and additions in news articles, future research could include interviews with journalists. Moreover, such qualitative data could help corroborate whether time constraints and/or article type influence how press releases are transformed into news coverage.

4.2. Representation of uncertainty

Regarding uncertainty, we show that most indicators are already absent in press releases, and that only some references to transitory uncertainty are presented. The apparent lack of references to permanent uncertainty has been ascribed previously to

limitations in measurement (Mazzi, Mitchell and Carausu, 2021). Calculating permanent uncertainty is challenging for large composite macroeconomic variables because the underlying data sources often report errors inconsistently or not at all (Mazzi, Mitchell and Carausu, 2021). This difficulty leads statistical offices to exercise caution when publishing information about permanent uncertainty, as illustrated by an explicit acknowledgement by the UK Office for National Statistics (Office for National Statistics, 2021). By contrast, transitory uncertainty is easier to indicate (Mazzi, Mitchell and Carausu, 2021), which could explain the observed occurrence in this study.

Moreover, the tendency to exclude permanent uncertainty has been supported by empirical research. Bles et al. (2019) examined press releases from the US and UK statistical offices and found that figures were often presented as point estimates, without explicit indications of uncertainty. Any uncertainty indicators or other caveats were typically included only in supporting information. In contrast, potential revisions to the data were occasionally noted, which aligns with our observation that press releases sometimes contain transitory uncertainty.

When transitory uncertainty was represented in the press release, we show that the majority of news articles still omit this information. However, such omission occurred less frequently if the uncertainty was presented explicitly in the press release rather than contextually. This result is consistent with previous findings that journalists often rely and partially reproduce the explicit information provided in the press release (Sumner *et al.*, 2014; Vonk, Bos and van Sebille, 2025). Nevertheless, even in these cases, uncertainty cues were reproduced in only a minority of articles. This suggests that while explicit cues increase the likelihood that uncertainty is transmitted from press releases to news coverage, journalists still selectively omit such information.

This observed pattern of omitting uncertainty in news reporting is consistent with previous research. Research in science communication consistently demonstrated that approximately 36-40% of news articles omit key conditional statements, such as study limitations and provisionality, thus giving the impression of enhanced certainty (Pellechia, 1997; Jensen, 2008; Guenther *et al.*, 2019). These omissions are often attributed to journalistic practices that prioritize simplification and newsworthiness, leading to the exclusion of more complex information such as uncertainty (Dempster, Sutherland and Keogh, 2022; Molina-Perez, Lempert and Wong, 2024). In line with the theory of news factors, this may indicate that expressions of uncertainty carry relatively low news value, and are therefore less likely to be preserved in news reporting. Future research could investigate whether the type of uncertainty indicator, for instance verbal or numerical qualifiers, affects its adoption in news communication. Still, the findings suggest that statistical agencies may enhance the transmission of uncertainty and contextual information by presenting such information more explicitly in press releases.

4.3. Representation of personalized sourcing

Personalized sourcing was completely absent in press releases, whereas news articles included both personalization and, to a greater extent, expert sources. The inclusion of personalized sourcing is illustrated by the following quotes from a news article on the labor market participation of Ukrainian refugees (Jaeger and Vos, 2025):

“Because Ukrainians are allowed to work immediately, they learn the language more quickly and enter employment sooner. Other asylum seekers often have to wait for years, which only increases their distance from the labour market.”

— Peter Hein Mulligen, head economist CBS (expert)

“When the war broke out, I came here with my children. I followed Dutch language classes at the University of Amsterdam and was able to start working quickly.”

— Lillia Frantsishko, Ukrainian refugee (personalization)

Thus, the results indicated that journalists frequently add personalized sourcing when reporting on CBS labor market statistics. Prior research indicates that journalists typically add expert voices to improve credibility and context, while personalization is used to enhance audience engagement (Conrad, 1999; Bossema *et al.*, 2019; Krämer and Peter, 2020; Vonk, Bos and van Sebille, 2025).

However, the observed relatively low occurrence of personalization remains notable, given its prevalence in science reporting. For example, a recent study on narrative techniques in news coverage of ocean plastic found that 99.2% of news articles ($n = 130$) and all original press releases ($n = 10$) included personalized representations of scientists (Vonk, Bos and van Sebille, 2025). This contrast suggests that the topic and genre of the press release may influence the extent to which personalization is incorporated. One possible explanation lies in differences in framing. Episodic framing, which focuses on individuals or specific events, naturally encourages personalization (Aarøe, 2011). In contrast, thematic framing emphasizes broader trends and structural developments (Krämer and Peter, 2020), which may be more typical for reporting on labor market statistics than science coverage.

The prominence of thematic framing is further supported by the frequent inclusion of expert sources. Approximately 60% of articles cite authoritative voices, primarily from CBS, universities or financial institutions, as also illustrated by the previous quote. These recognized institutional sources lend credibility and allow journalists to contextualize and explain statistical developments. Thus, by providing broad, interpretive information rather than focusing on individual experiences, expert commentary typically reinforces the thematic orientation (Iyengar, 1994).

However, another potential explanation for the relative infrequency of personalized sourcing concerns time constraints in news production. Reporting on official statistics is inherently time-sensitive, as their validity and relevance diminishes over time (ILO, 2017). Under such time constraints, journalists may have little opportunity to identify and include personal sources. This interpretation is supported by our finding that personalization is more common in articles based on embargoed press releases, though this result should be considered alongside the previously discussed limitation. Given that a similar pattern was observed for the inclusion of supplementary information from external sources (Table 4), these data suggest that time availability plays a broader role in shaping the content of news coverage.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the translation of CBS press releases into news articles involves selective preservation, omission and addition of information. First, the adoption of contextual information depended strongly on its type and associated news factors: technical details such as calculation adjustments and dataset specifications were often omitted, whereas information from external sources was frequently added. Second, when uncertainty was presented in the press release, it was most often omitted in subsequent news articles. Third, personalized sourcing was regularly introduced by journalists, with expert sourcing occurring more frequently than personalization. Finally, several information types were more frequently included in news articles based on embargoed press releases, suggesting that time availability influences the extent to which journalists include or omit specific types of information. Together, these findings highlight the active role of journalists in shaping how official statistics are communicated to the public and illustrate how content selection is guided by both news values and practical constraints. These results provide a basis for reflecting on how press releases could be structured to facilitate more accurate and consistent reporting in the media.

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7. AI statement

The tool Chatgpt (v5) was used to:

- Suggest sources for the introduction and discussion. These sources were individually evaluated for their applicability to the proposed research.
- Check spelling and grammar of the entire text. The reported errors and suggestions were incorporated in the text.
- Ask suggestion for the phrasing (but not content) of the title, research questions and the code book (appendix 2). These suggestions were evaluated and adapted to fit in my own phrasing.
- Aid in optimizing the R codes to make figures 2, 3 and 4. Specific alterations to the code were incorporated, which include altering the order of the graphs and having multiple axis titles.
- Suggest keywords for the study. These results were individually evaluated and the most applicable keywords were manually selected.
- Translate the used codebook to English for inclusion in the report (Appendix 2)

The tool NotebookLM (v1.14.0.) was used to:

- Provide summaries of the articles by Bles et al. (2019), Vonk, Bos and van Sebille (2025) and ILO (2017).

Appendix 1: query optimization

Introduction

The proposed research relies on a keyword-based search strategy to collect news articles for analysis. To optimize this data collection method, we first aim to find the most effective query parameters, particularly the maximum allowed distance between keywords. The goal is to minimize the inclusion of irrelevant articles, while maximizing the retrieval of relevant results.

For this purpose, a LexisNexis search was performed over a representative time period of 1-10-2025 up to 31-12-2025, while varying the maximum distance in the query (see below). The number of retrieved articles from the LexisNexis search were recorded, based on a manual evaluation of the relevancy of news articles. Articles were only considered relevant if they explicitly mentioned a CBS statistic that is related to the labor market, which includes (un)employment, vacancies, wages, social benefits or labor force composition.

(Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek) AND (arbeidsmarkt OR werkloos* OR werkgelegenheid OR "bijstandsuitkering*" OR baan* OR vacature*) W/x CBS

$x \in \{10,20,30,40,60,80\}$

Results

The results of the LexisNexis search indicate that an increase in word distance generally leads to an increase in the number of retrieved articles, both relevant and irrelevant (Table 6). However, no irrelevant articles are retrieved if a distance of up to 20 words is used. This threshold also results in the identification of 12 relevant results. Beyond 20 words, the proportion of irrelevant articles gradually increases, while a number of 4 additional relevant articles is identified.

Table 6. LexisNexis search results. The amount of articles, relevant and irrelevant, are represented as a function of the specified distance in the search query (x)

x	Total articles	Total relevant (%)	Total irrelevant (%)
10	10	10 (100%)	0 (0%)
20	12	12 (100%)	0 (0%)
30	16	15 (93.8%)	1 (6.2%)
40	17	15 (88.2%)	2 (11.8%)
60	18	16 (88.9%)	2 (11.1%)
80	21	16 (76.2%)	5 (23.8%)

Conclusion

Given that a maximum distance of 20 words eliminates all irrelevant articles, this threshold is adopted for the proposed study. Although increasing the distance could potentially retrieve additional relevant articles, the benefit of this is limited as sufficient numbers of articles can be identified over the full time period. Moreover, any articles that may be excluded are unlikely to systematically bias the results, as sentence structure and length in the news articles is not expected to be correlated with the inclusion or exclusion of supporting information.

Appendix 2: Codebook (English)

Coding instructions

- Read the full text before coding.
- Exclude an article from analysis if it does not contain a *figure* that (i) originates from CBS or (ii) relates to the labor market. The labor market includes the following categories: economy, (un)employment, vacancies, labor participation, composition of the workforce or social assistance benefits.
 - A *figure* is defined as a specific numerical value, statistic, or quantitative indicator presented in the article, such as counts, percentages, ratios, or averages.
- The unit of analysis is the entire article. However, for coding categories about uncertainty (9) and calculation adjustments (13), a specific analysis of the *highlighted figure* is required.
 - The *highlighted figure* is the **first figure from the CBS dataset mentioned in the newspaper article**. This same figure must also be identified and analyzed in the corresponding CBS article. If the highlighted figure is an abstraction of other figures (e.g., a 30% increase), also analyze the underlying figures.
- Group all news articles based on the corresponding CBS article. Each set is thus characterized by one CBS article.
- Only code the main text, including (sub)titles, lead, and highlighted sentences. Do not include contextual information such as figure captions or footnotes, unless explicitly stated as *contextual* in the coding variable.
- If a question is not applicable, code “x”.

Codebook

General

1. What is the set number?

Number:

2. What is the source of the article?

0 = CBS

1 = Algemeen Dagblad

2 = De Telegraaf

3 = De Volkskrant

4 = NRC Handelsblad

5 = Trouw

6 = NU.nl

7 = AD.nl

8 = NOS.nl

9 = Telegraaf.nl

10 = RTL.nl

3. What is the title of the article?

Title:

4. What is the highlighted figure?

Figure:

5. On what date was the article published?

Format: dd/mm/yyyy

6. What is the length of the article?

Number of words:

7. For CBS articles, was the article published under embargo?

If the press release concerns a standard monthly or quarterly article, code 'no'.

Otherwise, code 'yes'.

0 = no

1 = yes

8. For news articles, what is the Churnalism score with the original CBS article?

Number:

Uncertainty and Provisionality

9. Does the article mention uncertainty regarding the highlighted figure?

Transitory uncertainty: temporary uncertainty expected to decrease over time (e.g., provisional figures or later revisions). *Permanent uncertainty*: inherent uncertainty that does not decrease over time (e.g., limitations in sampling, methodology, or data coverage).

Uncertainty is coded as *explicit* if mentioned directly in the main text and *contextual* if mentioned elsewhere (e.g., footnotes or figure captions)

If both contextual and explicit uncertainty are present, code only explicit.

0 = no

1 = yes, contextual transitory uncertainty

2 = yes, explicit transitory uncertainty

3 = yes, contextual permanent uncertainty

4 = yes, explicit permanent uncertainty

Context

10. Does the article explicitly mention CBS as the source of the statistics?

0 = no

1 = yes

11. If CBS is mentioned, is the specific dataset also specified?

This refers to whether the article states the exact CBS dataset (e.g., Labour Force

Survey, publication *De arbeidsmarkt in cijfers*, or administrative records). Do not code vague references such as “new CBS figures.”

0 = no

1 = yes

12. Does the article include additional data from non-CBS sources?

This includes empirical information not part of the CBS dataset (e.g., UWV unemployment benefits, EU statistics, SCP research).

0 = no

1 = yes, only unemployment benefits, UWV not mentioned

2 = yes, only unemployment benefits, UWV explicitly mentioned

3 = yes, unemployment benefits + other non-CBS info, UWV not mentioned

4 = yes, unemployment benefits + other non-CBS info, UWV mentioned

5 = yes, non-CBS info, no unemployment benefits

13. Does the article indicate whether the highlighted figure is corrected for specific factors?

Corrections are coded as *explicit* if mentioned directly in the main text and *contextual* if mentioned elsewhere.

0 = no

1 = yes, contextual

2 = yes, explicit

14. Does the article place the CBS figures in a broader temporal context?

(e.g., trends, comparisons over time, “highest in four years”)

0 = no

1 = yes

15. Does the article describe the concept of unemployment?

0 = no mention

1 = mentioned, no description

2 = described incorrectly

3 = described correctly

16. Does the article describe the concept of underutilized labor potential (or subgroups)?

Includes: *semi-unemployed*, *underemployed part-time workers*

If multiple concepts are mentioned, all must be described

If one description is incorrect, then code as incorrect

0 = not mentioned

1 = mentioned, no description

2 = described incorrectly

3 = described correctly

Personalized Sourcing

17. How many individuals are quoted in the article?

Number:

18. Does the article contain personalization related to the figure?

Personalization is coded as individuals presented as actors or affected persons (not just a quote).

0 = no

1 = yes

19. If yes, what type of individual?

1 = employee

2 = unemployed/job seeker

3 = employer/entrepreneur

4 = other

20. Does the article cite at least one expert commenting on the CBS figures?

Expert is coded as someone with recognized authority (e.g., academic, policymaker).

0 = no

1 = yes

21. What is the affiliation of each expert?

1 = CBS

2 = employer/industry organization

3 = trade union

4 = university/researcher

5 = UWV

6 = financial institution (bank/insurance)

7 = government (non-CBS)

8 = other: ...

Appendix 3: Codebook (Dutch)

Codeerregels

- Lees vóór het coderen de volledige tekst.
- Sluit een artikel uit van analyse indien het geen cijfer bevat dat (i) afkomstig is van het CBS en (ii) betrekking heeft op de arbeidsmarkt. De arbeidsmarkt wordt omschreven met de volgende categorieën: economie, werkloosheid, vacatures, arbeidsparticipatie, samenstelling van de beroepsbevolking of uitkeringen.
 - Een cijfer wordt hierbij gedefinieerd als een specifieke numerieke waarde, statistiek of kwantitatieve indicator die in het artikel wordt gepresenteerd, zoals aantallen, percentages, ratio's of gemiddelden.
- De *Unit of analysis* is het gehele artikel, maar voor de coderingscategorieën 9 en 14 is een specifieke analyse van het uitgelichte cijfer noodzakelijk.
 - Het uitgelichte cijfer is het eerste cijfer uit de CBS dataset dat wordt genoemd in het krantenartikel. Ditzelfde cijfer dient ook te worden geïdentificeerd en geanalyseerd in het corresponderende CBS-artikel. Indien het uitgelichte cijfer een abstractie is van andere cijfers (bijvoorbeeld een 30% toename), analyseer dan de cijfers ook waarop het gebaseerd is.
- Groepeer alle nieuwsartikelen op basis van het bijbehorende CBS-artikel. Elke set wordt zo gekarakteriseerd door één CBS-artikel.
- Indien een set krantenartikelen verwijst naar meerdere uitgelichte cijfers, codeer de betreffende coderingsvragen (9 en 14) voor het CBS-artikel afzonderlijk op een nieuwe regel.
- Codeer uitsluitend de hoofdtekst inclusief (sub)titel, lead en uitgelichte zinnen. Neem geen contextuele informatie mee, zoals figuuronderschriften en voetnoten, tenzij bij de betreffende coderingsvariabele expliciet “contextueel” staat vermeld.
- Indien een vraag niet van toepassing is, codeer “x”.

Codeboek

Algemeen

1. **Wat is het nummer van de set?**

Number:

2. **Wat is de bron van het artikel?**

0 = CBS

1 = Algemeen Dagblad

2 = De Telegraaf

- 3 = De Volkskrant
- 4 = NRC Handelsblad
- 5 = Trouw
- 6 = NU.nl
- 7 = AD.nl
- 8 = NOS.nl
- 9 = Telegraaf.nl
- 10 = RTL.nl

3. **Wat is de titel van het artikel?**

Titel:

4. **Wat is het uitgelichte cijfer?**

Cijfer:

5. **Op welke datum is het artikel gepubliceerd?**

Datum: dd/mm/jjjj

6. **Wat is de lengte van het artikel?**

Aantal woorden:

7. **Voor CBS artikelen, is het artikel onder embargo gepubliceerd?**

0 = nee

1 = ja

8. **Voor nieuws artikelen, wat is de *Churnalism score* met het oorspronkelijke CBS artikel?**

Nummer:

Onzekerheid

9. **Wordt in het artikel onzekerheid genoemd met betrekking tot het uitgelichte cijfer?**

Transiënte onzekerheid verwijst naar tijdelijke onzekerheid die naar verwachting in de tijd afneemt, bijvoorbeeld doordat cijfers voorlopig zijn of later worden herzien.

Permanente onzekerheid verwijst naar onzekerheid die inherent is aan de data of meetmethode en niet afneemt in de tijd, zoals beperkingen in steekproeven, methodologie of datadekking.

Onzekerheid wordt gecodeerd als *expliciet* wanneer deze rechtstreeks in de hoofdtekst wordt genoemd, en als *contextueel* wanneer deze elders wordt aangegeven, bijvoorbeeld in een voetnoot of figuuronderschrift.

Indien zowel contextuele als expliciete onzekerheid voorkomt, codeer uitsluitend expliciete onzekerheid. Indien er zowel *transiënte* en *permanente* onzekerheid in zit, codeer dan beide overeenkomstige nummers, bijvoorbeeld "2, 3".

0 = nee

1 = ja, contextuele transiënte onzekerheid

- 2 = ja, expliciete transiënte onzekerheid
- 3 = ja, contextuele permanente onzekerheid
- 4 = ja, expliciete permanente onzekerheid

Context

10. Benoemt het artikel CBS expliciet als bron van de statistische cijfers?

- 0 = nee
- 1 = ja

11. Als CBS als bron wordt benoemd, wordt dan ook de directe databron nader gespecificeerd?

Hiermee wordt bedoeld of het artikel vermeldt uit welke specifieke dataset van het CBS de cijfers afkomstig zijn, zoals de Enquête Beroepsbevolking bij werkloosheidscijfers, publicatie De arbeidsmarkt in cijfers of de polisadministratie bij aantal banen. Codeer geen ongespecificeerde bronnen, zoals “nieuwe cijfers van het CBS”.

- 0 = nee
- 1 = ja

12. Bevat het artikel aanvullende cijfers, data, statistieken of andere empirische informatie afkomstig van een bron buiten het CBS?

Dit verwijst naar cijfers of empirische gegevens die geen onderdeel zijn van de CBS-dataset. Onder *empirische informatie* wordt verstaan: informatie die gebaseerd is op systematische waarneming, meting of registratie, zoals kwantitatieve cijfers of op feiten gebaseerde onderzoeksresultaten. Voorbeelden zijn cijfers over WW-uitkeringen van het UWV, alternatieve arbeidsmarktstatistieken van de Europese Unie of onderzoeken van het SCP over de attitudes van mannen en vrouwen op de arbeidsmarkt. Empirische informatie hoeft dus niet alleen directe cijfers te betreffen, feiten of schattingen tellen ook. Indien er cijfers in het artikel voorkomen waarvan de bron onduidelijk is, controleer dan in het corresponderende CBS-artikel of deze cijfers onderdeel zijn van de CBS-dataset.

- 0 = nee
- 1 = ja, uitsluitend WW-uitkeringen, UWV niet genoemd als bron
- 2 = ja, uitsluitend WW-uitkeringen, UWV expliciet genoemd als bron
- 3 = ja, WW-uitkeringen én andere aanvullende informatie van niet-CBS-bronnen, UWV niet genoemd als bron voor WW
- 4 = ja, WW-uitkeringen én andere aanvullende informatie van niet-CBS-bronnen, UWV expliciet genoemd als bron voor WW
- 5 = ja, aanvullende informatie van niet-CBS-bronnen, geen WW-uitkeringen genoemd

13. Vermeldt het artikel of het uitgelichte cijfer is gecorrigeerd voor specifieke factoren?

Correcties worden gecodeerd als *expliciet* wanneer deze rechtstreeks in de hoofdtekst wordt genoemd, en als *contextueel* wanneer deze elders wordt aangegeven, bijvoorbeeld in een voetnoot of figuuronderschrift

0 = nee

1 = ja, als contextuele informatie

2 = ja, als expliciete informatie

14. Plaatst het artikel de CBS cijfers in een bredere temporele context?

Dit betreft of het artikel de cijfers positioneert binnen een trend, ontwikkeling of vergelijking over tijd, in plaats van het als een los momentopname te presenteren. Voorbeelden zijn het noemen van hetzelfde cijfer in een andere periode of aangeven dat het uitzonderlijk hoog of laag is binnen een bepaalde tijdsperiode (bijvoorbeeld “het hoogste niveau in vier jaar”)

0 = nee

1 = ja

15. Geeft het artikel een beschrijving van het concept werkloosheid, of waar het uit bestaat?

Werkloosheid is het verschijnsel dat personen zonder betaald werk, die recent hebben gezocht en direct beschikbaar zijn, geen baan kunnen krijgen.

Voorbeelden van een beschrijving zijn: een expliciete definitie of een toelichting op de kenmerken of bevolkingsstromen waaruit werkloosheid bestaat.

0 = nee, het artikel benoemt geen werkloosheid

1 = nee, het artikel noemt werkloosheid maar geeft geen verdere beschrijving

2 = ja, het artikel benoemt werkloosheid maar de beschrijving is in tegenspraak met de CBS definitie

3 = ja, het artikel benoemt werkloosheid en de beschrijving is niet in tegenspraak met de CBS definitie

16. Geeft het artikel een beschrijving van het concept onbenut arbeidspotentieel of een van de subgroepen (semiwerklozen, onderbenutte deeltijdwerkers)?

On(der)benut arbeidspotentieel verwijst naar het deel van de bevolking dat wel potentieel inzetbaar is op de arbeidsmarkt, maar momenteel niet of niet volledig wordt benut. Het omvat: (1) semiwerklozen, die óf recent naar werk hebben gezocht maar niet direct beschikbaar zijn, óf wel direct beschikbaar zijn maar niet recent naar werk hebben gezocht, en (2) onderbenutte deeltijdwerkers, die in deeltijd werken, meer uren willen werken en hiervoor op korte termijn beschikbaar zijn.

Als het artikel meer dan één concept/subgroep noemt, codeer dan alleen als er voor elk genoemd concept/subgroep een beschrijving wordt gegeven.

Beoordeel vervolgens de correctheid van alle beschrijvingen samen: als één van de beschrijvingen niet correct is, wordt dit meegenomen bij het bepalen van de code.

0 = nee, het artikel benoemt geen onbenut arbeidspotentieel of een van de subgroepen

1 = nee, het artikel noemt het concept en/of een subgroep maar geeft geen verdere beschrijving

2 = ja, het artikel benoemt het concept en/of een subgroep met beschrijving maar de beschrijving is in tegenspraak met de CBS definitie

3 = ja, het artikel benoemt onbenut arbeidspotentieel en/of een subgroep met beschrijving en de beschrijving is niet in tegenspraak met de CBS

Gepersonaliseerde bronverwijzing

17. Hoeveel verschillende individuen worden in het artikel geciteerd?

Aantal:

18. Bevat het artikel een vorm van personalisering dat in relatie staat tot het cijfer?

Personalisering verwijst naar het opnemen van specifieke individuen die handelen of direct worden geraakt door de beschreven ontwikkeling. Een enkele citaat of verwijzing is op zichzelf geen personalisering. Codeer personalisering alleen wanneer individuen worden neergezet als actieve actoren of expliciet reageren vanuit persoonlijke ervaring

0 = no

1 = yes

19. Indien personalisering aanwezig is, welk type individu wordt geportretteerd?

1 = Werknemer

2 = Werkloze/werkzoekende

3 = Werkgever/ondernemer

4 = Anders, namelijk

20. Citeert of quote het artikel minstens één expert die commentaar geeft op een trend of gebeurtenis die gerelateerd is aan de CBS cijfers?

Expertcitatie verwijst naar het opnemen van een verklaring, uitleg of interpretatie van de statistische cijfers door een persoon waarbij expliciet wordt verwezen naar diens (relevante) expertise of autoriteit, zoals een academisch onderzoeker of overheidsfunctionaris. Codeer geen expert wanneer deze de CBS cijfers zelf benoemt.

0 = nee

1 = ja

21. Wat is de affiliatie van elke expert?

1 = CBS

- 2 = Werkgever- of brancheorganisatie
- 3 = Vakbond
- 4 = Universiteit of ander soort onderzoeker
- 5 = UWV
- 6 = Financiële instelling/bank/verzekeraar
- 7 = Overheid (niet-CBS)
- 8 = Overig, namelijk ...

Appendix 4: intercoder reliability results

Table 7. Intercoder reliability measures. Cohen kappa of the different coded variables, corresponding to the questions in the codebook (appendix 2).

Coded variable	Kappa
Uncertainty	0.93
Source	1.00
Dataset	1.00
Adjustments	0.90
Information	0.82
Period	0.84
Personalization	1.00
Personalization affiliation	1.00
Expert	1.00
Expert affiliation	1.00
<i>Average</i>	<i>0.95</i>

Appendix 5: Analysis of additional contextual information

Figure 6. Preservation of concepts in news articles. Distribution of news articles that mentioned the concepts *unemployment* (A) and *unused labor potential* (B) with or without a description.

Figure 7. Preservation of UWV source reference in news articles. Distribution of news articles that mentioned the concept *social assistance benefit* with or without a source reference to the institution UWV.